

WAYS TO IMPROVE INTERNAL AUDIT ACTIVITY IN COMMERCIAL BANKS

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Abstract. *The main factors in improving the internal audit activity of commercial banks are that its improvement provides the opportunity to reduce the operational costs of banking activities and identify and eliminate existing risks in advance. In this dissertation, the internal audit in the activity of Uzsanotkurulishbank is studied. Also, the analysis of financial and economic conditions in commercial banks, the analysis of views and theories of foreign and local scientists, the regulatory and legal bases of the development of the audit system in banks were researched. The existing internal audit situation for the Self-Construction Bank is analyzed and practical recommendations and suggestions are given based on foreign experiences.*

Keywords: *commercial banks, internal audit, corporate management, operational expenses.*

INTRODUCTION. An important issue in the organization and operation of commercial banks in Uzbekistan is internal control of internal banking operations, which is important for determining the efficiency of banks. Because this control, first of all, serves as a basis for effective organization of banking activities and prevention of excessive expenses, organization of efficient operation of the bank.

Analyzing the results of economic and financial activities carried out by commercial banks and monitoring their correct implementation undoubtedly ensures the financial stability of banks. This process provides opportunities to monitor all operations of a commercial bank and to eliminate any deficiencies in time.

Also, in the new version of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan O'RQ-582 dated November 11, 2019 on amendments and additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan", the Central Bank the need to specify the requirements for internal audit of banks, microfinance organizations, mortgage refinancing organizations and credit bureaus in the tasks related to control. At the same time, in the new version of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 5, 2019 O'RQ-580 on amendments and additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Banks and Banking Activities", Corporate the organizational structure, procedures and mechanisms of management should be complex and should be consistent with the nature, scale and complexity of the risks inherent in the business model and activities of the bank. Internal control mechanisms should at least ensure that management tasks are performed and risks are assessed and internal audit requirements are met, organization of the bank's internal audit service, as well as assessment of bank management's compliance with bank strategies and policies based on quarterly reports of the bank's internal audit service such tasks are defined.

In addition, based on the decision of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 3/2 of April 16, 2021, the Regulation on the requirements for the internal audit of commercial banks was approved. This Regulation was registered by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of

Uzbekistan on May 7, 2021, registration number 3302. In this case, it is determined that the Bank's supervisory board should organize the internal audit service and ensure its effective operation.

Literature review. Economic activity in countries is mainly organized and financed by banks. Due to the financing function of banks, the problems that banks may face in the banking system have a serious impact on the state economy. Therefore, effective organization of bank audits is required (Zengin and Yu'ksel, 2016).

Many audit activities are carried out in banks. These audit activities are mainly carried out by internal control and internal audit departments. In addition to internal control and internal audit, banks are audited by independent auditors and external government auditors (Yurtsever, 2009).

Internal audit is an objective set of measures to control and assess the correctness of transactions related to the financial and economic activities of the enterprise, to identify deficiencies and to eliminate them. Also, the purpose of internal audit in commercial banks is to ensure the reliability of the financial statements of the bank being prepared and to deliver reliable information to interested parties.

Also, as the main goals of the organization of the internal audit in general, regulation, control, assessment and improvement of the efficiency of the internal activities of the enterprise, development of recommendations on the identification of possible risks, their evaluation and management, organization of the efficient use of the resources of the enterprise and ensuring compliance of the internal policy with the normative and legal frameworks.

Audit committees or audit commissions of enterprises are of course important in the implementation of these tasks. Audit commissions develop recommendations for strengthening the internal control and audit system, checking financial reports, and improving the efficiency of the enterprise. One of the important aspects of audit activity is to ensure independence of auditors. The reporting of internal auditors to audit commissions and the accountability of independent auditors to audit commissions are important. In order to ensure the independence of auditors, it is a common practice to establish audit commissions within the board of directors in banks.

Internal audit is an important tool for managing the powers and procedures of any organization. According to Dellai and Omri (2016), according to the functions of internal audit, it is important to ensure compliance in the organization, effective organization of financial management and protection of assets.

The internal audit department of organizations is an important department, because it is considered necessary to use the accounting information system, which helps to effectively evaluate the activities of this agency in the long run. Internal audit is mainly crucial in corporate accounting, because now it has to record all procedures related to commerce.

A successful internal audit will allow the company to expand as the financial report shows how effective the internal auditor is. Provides opportunities to develop additional monitoring procedures to ensure the accuracy of data reporting by company directors and audit committees.

Effective internal systems underpin a corporation's corporate and financial strategy, and internal audit is critical to improving the reliability of these systems, improving risk management, and meeting the demands of internal users.

Accountability of employees and executives to investors and other shareholders is improved through internal auditing (Eighme & Cashell, 2002).

The audit board, the company's board of directors and the organization's administration benefit from the impartial, reliable service of the internal audit department. It provides real

information on the returns of investors, sustainable growth, effective management and economic performance of the corporation and corporate behavior, i.e. information on other issues of interest to interested parties.

Keeping quality under control is essential to protect organizations from the risk of accidents. Every institution strives to do this, so it is assumed that institutions audited by qualified auditors are likely to have a lower level of risk (Davidson et al., 2005).

The role of the internal auditor is to increase the ability of organizations to create value by providing monitoring and follow-up to improve performance (Coram, Ferguson, and Moroney 2008).

In addition, internal audit is an important tool for organizations to use corporate results. Internal audit efficiency significantly increases added value and improves performance (Postula, Irodenko & Dubel 2020).

Methodology. By carrying out a literature review in the course of research, the research conducted by scientists before us and their results are studied and analyzed. The method of positivism is used as a direction of research based on the results of the analysis. Our research is mainly based on quantitative indicators.

We also select scientific research methods on the basis of studied literature and scientific research. The methods used for the analysis in the research are quantitative indicators analysis methods, horizontal and vertical analysis, analysis of relative indicators and correlation and regression analysis on their interrelationships, and the results of the analysis conclusions are given. Scientifically based proposals and recommendations are developed based on the conclusions.

Results and analysis. As one of the oldest banks in Uzbekistan, its activity has undergone a number of changes, renaming and improvement, and it has always been a reliable partner for its clients and an active participant in the financial and economic life of the country.

"Uzsanoatqurilishbank" ATB was established on October 28, 1922 as the Central Asian office of the commercial and industrial bank in Tashkent. Also, in October 1924, the bank began working as a government agent for financing and lending to the public sector. Over the next 10 years of independence, Uzsanoatqurilishbank financed strategic projects in the energy and oil and gas sectors. According to further reforms, in 2009 the bank was given a new name - "Uzsanoatqurilishbank" joint-stock commercial bank. In 2018, rebranding and improvement of business processes were carried out.

Regarding its participation in the financial market, in 2019 Uzsanoatqurilishbank issued the first 300 million dollar corporate Eurobonds in the country's history.

In 2020, as part of reforms in the digitalization system, it launched a new "JOYDA" mobile application, which combines banking services and various products in the form of a Marketplace.

"Uzsanoatqurilishbank" joint-stock commercial bank received awards for its stable activity in 2021 and 2022. In 2023, the bank was recognized by YETTB for its role in the development of energy-saving technologies in Uzbekistan.

The main major shareholders of the bank include the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Recovery and Development Fund of the Republic of Uzbekistan and enterprises of the basic sectors of the economy.

Other shareholders of "Uzsanoatqurilishbank" ADB include "Uztransgaz" JSC, Bukhara Oil Refinery, Fergana Oil Refinery, "Tashkent Thermal Power Plant" LLC, "Absolute Investments Trust" LLC, "Talimarjon IES" LLC. , "Uzbekenergo" JSC, "Asset Invest Trust" LLC, "Uzbekistan

Temir Yo'llari" DATK, "Shortan gas chemical complex" UshK included a number of organizations.

The nominal value of a bank share is 19 (nineteen) soums. The authorized capital of the bank is 4 634 513 904 398 (four trillion six hundred thirty four billion five hundred thirteen million nine hundred four thousand three hundred ninety eight) soums and it is divided into the following shares:

- the total cost is 4 627 483 904 398 (four trillion six hundred twenty seven billion four hundred eighty three million nine hundred four thousand three hundred ninety eight) soums 243 551 784 442 (two hundred forty three billion five hundred fifty one million seven hundred eighty four thousand four hundred forty two) ordinary shares bearing the name of the owner;

- 370,000,000 (three hundred and seventy million) preferred shares with a total value of 7,030,000,000 (seven billion and thirty million) soums with the owner's name written on them.

"Uzsanoatqurilishbank" ATB is a commercial organization that performs a set of operations defined as banking activities on opening and maintaining bank accounts, making payments, attracting funds to deposits (deposits), granting loans on its own behalf A legal entity is called a bank.

"Uzsanoatqurilishbank" ATB have the right to carry out the financial operations specified in the license granting the right to carry out banking activities. The subject of the bank's activity is money, currency values and other financial instruments. The maximum effective implementation of monetary functions in the form of banking services is the subject of banking activity. A bank is a commercial organization whose main goal is to make a profit, and is independent in making decisions regarding the implementation of banking operations. The bank is a universal bank and is part of the unified banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Figure 1. "Uzsanoatqurilishbank" ATB, dynamic changes in bank activity income and NPL indicators in 2021-2023.

The main part of Uzsanoatqurilishbank's banking activity is income. It can be seen from the above analysis that the amount of income received from the effective circulation of deposit and loan amounts and the services rendered to the bank's clients amounted to 6.6 trillion soums in 2021, and in 2022 reached 8.3 trillion soums. He also indicated the amount of income of 11.1 trillion soums by the end of 2023.

Also, the main risk of banking risks is the fact that loan amounts are not returned on time and there are increasing trends in the amount of problem loans. In the next picture, we can see that the amount of the share of problem loans showed decreasing trends for 2021-2023. In 2021, the NPL indicator was 3.8 percent, and in 2022 it was 2.8 percent. We can see that by 2023 it will be 2.3 percent and will decrease by 0.5 percent and will decrease by 1.5 percent compared to 2021.

For these positive results, "Uzsanoatkurilishbank" established cooperation with major international financial institutions. In 2019-2020, according to the results of its activities, the bank engaged more than 20 experts of the National Institute of Economic and Social Development of Ukraine and ETTB for the transformation of 18 areas. As a result, the following changes were made:

- the corporate management system was improved, 5 foreign independent members were included in the Bank's board;
- 5 committees were established under the bank board;
- the organizational structure was adapted to international standards;
- customers were divided into 3 segments (corporate business, small and medium business, retail business) and structural departments were established to work with them;
- RM managers were introduced to provide individual customer service;
- an underwriting system was introduced for effective credit risk management.

Also, 55 top managers were trained at the Skolkovo Moscow School of Management for the results of the bank's activity in 2023. A number of changes have also been made:

- improved information and cyber security system;
- the contact center was transformed into a sales channel;
- the share of customer service employees reached 59%
- a business process management office was established.

Having positively evaluated the results of this activity, "Uzsanoatqurulishbank" determined its strategic indicators for 2024-2026.

According to the net profit and profitability indicators of its goals for the next years, the bank predicts 1.5 trillion soums by the end of 2024. According to these indicators, 2 trillion soums and 2.9 trillion soums are forecast for 2025 and 2026, respectively. Also, according to profitability indicators, the strategic indicators of profitability of assets for 2024-2026 were 2 percent, 2.3 percent, and 2.9 percent, respectively.

If the return on capital is planned to be the same amount for 2024 and 2025, i.e. 17 percent, by 2026 this amount is forecast to reach 18.7 percent.

Positive changes for other indicators are definitely predicted for this forecasted amount. Changes in assets alone are planned to amount to 82.3 trillion soums in 2024, and by 2026 it is forecast to increase to 40 trillion soums.

It is also planned to double the amount of capital by 2026 compared to 2024, and these amounts are planned to increase to 9.9 trillion soums in 2024, 14.1 trillion soums in 2025, and 17 trillion soums in 2026. At the same time, it is planned to increase the loan portfolio, and by 2026 it is planned to increase the amount of the loan portfolio to 75.3 trillion soums and to increase it by 15 trillion soums compared to 2024. In 2024, the loan portfolio is planned to be 59.5 trillion soums, and in 2025 it is planned to reach 69.2 trillion soums. In addition, it is planned to increase the amount of deposits. In 2024, the amount of deposits is planned to be 22.4 trillion soums, and in 2026 it is forecasted to be 34.8 trillion soums.

In terms of the amount of these indicators, it is planned to increase assets by 12.3%, loan portfolio by 13.8%, deposit portfolio by 8.6%, capital by 13.4%, and net profit by 9.4%.

Figure 2. The main strategic goals of Uzsanotkurilishbank ATB for 2024-2026.

According to Article 16 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 5, 2019 "On Amendments and Additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Banks and Banking Activities" No. in order to issue a preliminary permission for the establishment" of the bank's internal audit, the organizational structure, procedures and mechanisms of the corporate management should be complex, and the nature of the risks inherent in the business model and activities of the bank , scale and complexity should be appropriate. Internal control mechanisms should at least ensure that management tasks are performed and risks are assessed and internal audit requirements are met.

In addition, based on the decision No. 3/2 of the management of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the regulation on requirements for internal audit of commercial banks", the Regulation on requirements for internal audit of commercial banks approved. This Regulation was registered by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 7, 2021, registration number 3302.

This regulation states that the audit service should independently analyze and evaluate the following:

- taking into account the bank's risk profile, the effectiveness of internal control, including the fight against money laundering, terrorist financing and the financing of the proliferation of weapons of mass destruction, compliance control, risk management and corporate governance systems and their correctness that it has been launched;

- the effectiveness of bank business processes, administrative and operational processes in achieving the goals set for the bank,

- the reliability, completeness and efficiency of information systems, as well as the relevance, accuracy, convenience, and confidentiality of information;

- compliance with legal documents, including prudential requirements of the Central Bank and internal documents of the bank;

- that the deficiencies identified by the Central Bank, other state bodies and external audits have been eliminated in time;

examines the efficiency of the system of consideration of appeals of citizens and legal entities.

Also, the Internal Audit Service checks at least the following when assessing the risk management system:

Based on the activities of the structural unit on risk management, including the decisions made by this structural unit, as well as its tasks and powers, the risk management system (credit, liquidity, market, operational, compliance, etc.) is correct that it has been launched;

the bank's risk appetite and that the bank's activity is within the risk appetite;

that information on risk management, including major risks, is submitted to the Central Bank, the board and management;

that the risk management system, including the identification, measurement, evaluation, management, timely action and accountability processes of risks arising in the banking activity, are properly established;

the acceptability of risk management information systems, the accuracy, reliability and completeness of information in them;

the development of risk assessment methods and their use, including the sequence of risk assessment stages and the relevance and reliability of the data used in the methods. During the audit of the compliance control service, compliance with legal documents and internal documents of the bank, including the effectiveness of risk management related to the legalization of proceeds from criminal activities, the financing of terrorism and the financing of the distribution of weapons of mass destruction are evaluated.

CONCLUSION. Effective organization of internal audit functions is important for commercial banks to successfully deal with the complexities of the modern banking environment. By prioritizing independence, professional competence, technology adoption, communication, and alignment with organizational goals, banks can increase the value of their internal audit functions. Continuous improvement, proactive risk management, and a culture of accountability are key factors for optimizing internal audit performance and achieving long-term success in commercial banking operations.

REFERENCES

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "On Amendments and Additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated 11.11.2019 No. ORQ-582.
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "On Amendments and Additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Banks and Banking Activities" No. ORQ-580 of 05.11.2019.
3. Zengin, S., & Yu'ksel, S. (2016). Affecting factor of liquidity Risks: An examination on Turkish banking sector. *Istanbul Ticaret University Social Sciences Journal*, 15(29), 77e95.
4. Yurtsever, G. (2009). *Bank inspectorate from inspection to internal audit*. Istanbul: The Bank Association of Turkey Publications.
5. Dellai, H., & Omri, M. A. B. (2016). Factors Affecting the Internal Effectiveness in Tunisian organizations. *Research journal of Finance and Accounting*, 7, 208-2011
6. Eighme, J., Cashell, J. (2002). Internal auditors' roles in overcoming the financial reporting crisis. *International Auditing*, 17, 3-10.

7. Davidson, R., Goodwin-Stewart, J., Kent, P. (2005,). Internal Governance Structures and Earnings Management. *Accounting and Finance*, 45, 241-267.
8. Coram, P., Ferguson & Moroney, R. (2008). The extent of asset theft fraud, alternative internal audit frameworks, and internal audit. *Accounting and Finance journal*, 48(4), 543-559
9. Marta Postula, Olga Irodenko, Przemyslaw Dubel Internal Audit as a Tool to Improve the Efficiency of Public Service *European Research Studies Journal*, Volume XXIII, Issue 3, 699-715, 2020 DOI: 10.35808/ersj/1663